

Enhancing Cure Kinetics Estimation for Thermosetting Carbon Fiber-Epoxy Prepregs Through Chemistry-Informed Machine Learning

Geun Young Kim, Shreyes N. Melkote, Jonathan S. Colton
Georgia Institute of Technology

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 - Exothermic reactions in composite manufacturing
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Manufacturer's Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC)

- Each resin system has its own cure cycle for best performance

Cycom 5320-1

Toray 3900

Exothermic Reactions in Composite

- Produce significant temperature gradient along the part, leading to defects

Hexcel 8552 resin system, Zhang et.al (2021)

Cure defects, Wang et.al (2022)

→ Consider cure kinetics to predict how much heat will be generated

Modeling Methods of Cure Kinetics

Fundamental

Table 1
Monomer structure, characteristics and nomenclature

Monomer	Formula	Molar mass (g mol ⁻¹)	Melting point (°C)
Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A		349	45
<i>p</i> -Toluidine		107	43
4,4'-Diamino diphenyl methane		198	80

Polymerization of Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA), Blanco, et. al (2022)

Phenomenological

Differential Scanning Calorimetry, Hardis, et. al (2013)

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Phenomenological Approach

Pros

Cons

Model free kinetics (MFK)

$$\frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} = K_{\alpha_i} f(\alpha_i),$$

$$\text{where } K_{\alpha_i} = A_{\alpha_i} \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\alpha_i}}{RT}\right)$$

Coefficients

Model-independent

Implementation

Isoconversional method

Applicability

Only for single-step reaction

Multivariate regression

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K_1(1 - \alpha)^{n_1} + K_2\alpha^{m_2}(1 - \alpha)^{n_2} + \dots$$

$$\text{where } K_i = A_i \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{RT}\right)$$

Implementation

Least square method

Applicability

Represent multi-step reaction

Coefficients

Rely on initial guess & model

Research Objectives

To build a **neural network-based** cure kinetics model that captures cure kinetics **efficiently**, with the following characteristics:

- Model architecture handles:

- ✓ **Numerical stability**

- ✓ **Chemical validity**

Model Selection Strategy

Scenario based model selection

Traditional NN validation accuracy
→ Constant heating rate cycle

Proposed method
→ Manufacturer's recommended cure cycle

Model Architecture

Previous work on NN based approach (Hui, 2022)

Model Architecture

Chemistry-informed Neural Network (CINN)

Dataset

- $(1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min} \sim 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}) \times (80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \sim 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}, 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}\text{ increment}) = \underline{2210\text{ data points}}$
- Assumption: Initial degree of cure of uncured prepreg = 0

A	B	C	D	E
	Temperature (C)	Reaction Rate	Ramp rate (C/min)	Degree of Cure
40	120	3.20E-06	10	3.45E-05
41	121	8.07E-07	10	4.66E-05
42	122	4.31E-06	10	6.19E-05
43	123	1.92E-06	10	8.06E-05
44	124	5.43E-06	10	0.000102696
45	125	3.04E-06	10	0.000128114
46	126	6.55E-06	10	0.000156884
47	127	4.16E-06	10	0.000189006
48	128	7.67E-06	10	0.00022448
49	129	5.28E-06	10	0.000263305
50	130	8.78E-06	10	0.000305482
51	131	1.23E-05	10	0.000368701
52	132	1.58E-05	10	0.000452962
53	133	1.93E-05	10	0.000558266
54	134	2.28E-05	10	0.000684611
55	135	2.63E-05	10	0.000831999
56	136	2.98E-05	10	0.001000429
57	137	3.92E-05	10	0.001207592
58	138	4.27E-05	10	0.001453488
59	139	5.21E-05	10	0.001738116
60	140	5.56E-05	10	0.002061476

Experimental Setup

- Material: Toray T830H 6K/3900-2D carbon fiber prepreg
- Sample mass: 11 ~ 15 mg
- Pan & lid: T-zero Hermetic

DSC: Q2000 (TA Instruments)

Oven: HAFO 1602

Training Accuracy

Goodness of the fit to the trained curve

- Closely matches DSC curve, but Hui's model shows a negative reaction rate

Validation Accuracy

Both models show minimum error at 1500 epochs

- 60-minute hold : 4.9% relative error (CINN)
- 120-minute hold: 0.9% relative error (CINN)

Robustness Tests

Thermal disturbance

- 4 Samples
- Each of a part size: 12 mm x 12 mm x 0.25 mm
- Cure cycle: Varies

Fabrication

- Part size: 300 mm x 300 mm x 12.5 mm
- Cure cycle: MRCC (3 hours hold)

Thermal Disturbance Test

- Measured
- CINN
- Dykeman (2008)
- Hui et al. (2022)

All models match well

Fabrication Test

- CINN showed similar trend, even outperforming the Dykeman's model
- Hui's model starts to deviate as temperature reaches peak and hold
→ Overestimates heating rate

Conclusion

- Chemistry-induced neural network model (CINN) showed not only high accuracy but also numerical stability and chemical validity.
- Scenario based selected model showed consistent performance.

Future Plans

- Test using different resin systems for generalizability
- Elaborate model selection method

Thank you for your kind attention

Ph.D. Student, Geun Young Kim
George W. Woodruff School of Mechanical engineering
Georgia Institute of Technology
✉ gkim439@gatech.edu

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Appendix: Dykeman's Model (Dykeman, 2008)

Total Model:

$$\dot{\alpha} = K_{1eff}(1-\alpha)^{n_1} + K_{2eff}\alpha^{m_2}(1-\alpha)^{n_2} + K_{3eff}\alpha^{m_3}(1-\alpha)^{n_3} \quad 5.19$$

Chemical Reaction:

$$\dot{\alpha} = K_1(1-\alpha)^{n_1} + K_2\alpha^{m_2}(1-\alpha)^{n_2} + K_3\alpha^{m_3}(1-\alpha)^{n_3}$$

Primary-Amine and Epoxy:

If $T < 124^\circ\text{C}$ and $\alpha < 0.035$, Then $A_1 = 34378 \cdot \ln(\alpha) + 229563$ /sec and $E_1 = 73300$ J/mol;

If $A_1 < 50000$ /sec, Then $A_1 = 50000$ /sec.

End If.

Else, If $T < 124^\circ\text{C}$ and $\alpha > 0.035$, Then $A_1 = 113881$ /sec and $E_1 = 73300$ J/mol;

Else, If $T > 124^\circ\text{C}$, Then $A_1 = 14240$ /sec and $E_1 = 66435$ J/mol.

End If.

Secondary-Amine and Epoxy: $A_2 = 473684$ /sec, $E_2 = 73063$ J/mol

Etherification: $A_3 = 1.5\text{E}9$ /sec, $E_3 = 115624$ J/mol

Reaction Orders:

$m_1 = 0, n_1 = 1$

$m_2 = 1, n_2 = 2.5$

$m_3 = 2.91, n_3 = 0.83$

Appendix: Dykeman's Model (cont.)

Tg- α :

$$Tg = \frac{\lambda\alpha(Tg_{\infty} - Tg_0)}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha} + Tg_0 + \frac{D}{1 + \exp[-F(\alpha - \alpha_{critical})]}$$

λ (copolymer) = 0.8, Tg_0 = 8.8°C, Tg_{∞} (copolymer) = 200°C, D = 35, F = 25

Tg_{∞} (epoxy) \geq 222°C

$\alpha_{critical}$:

If $dT/dt < 0.0001$ K/sec, Then $\alpha_{critical} = (0.0025 / K) * T - 0.3329$;

Else, $\alpha_{critical} = (0.0025 / K) * T - (0.00017K / \text{sec}) / \dot{T} - 0.3329$.

End If.

If $\alpha_{critical} < 0.675$, Then $\alpha_{critical} = 0.675$.

End If.

If $\alpha_{critical} > 1$, Then $\alpha_{critical} = 1$.

End If.

Diffusion:

Primary and secondary amine reactions with epoxide:

$$k_{d1,2} = A_{d1,2} \exp\left(-\frac{E_{d1,2}}{RT} - \frac{b_{1,2}}{f_v}\right)$$

$A_{d1,2} = 4E12$ /sec, $E_{d1,2} = 60$ kJ/mol, $b_{1,2} = 0.52$, and $f_v = a_f(T-Tg) + f_g$, $a_f = 0.00008$ /°C, $f_g = 0.025$

If $T-Tg < -50$ K, Then $K_{d1,2} = 1E-99$ /sec

End If.

Etherification:

$$k_{d3} = A_{d3} \exp\left(-\frac{b_3}{f_v}\right)$$

$A_{d3} = 1.5E9$ /sec, $b_3 = 0.7$, and $f_v = a_f(T-Tg) + f_g$, $a_f = 0.00008$ /°C, $f_g = 0.025$

If $T-Tg < -50$ K, Then $K_{d3} = 1E-99$ /sec

End If.

$k_{d1,2}$ and k_{d3} are added to k_1 , k_2 and k_3 chemical by the Rabinowitch equation:

$$\frac{1}{K_e} = \frac{1}{K_c} + \frac{1}{K_d}$$

Appendix: Validation Loss

Traditional training – validation loss

Scenario-based validation loss

Appendix: Surface Response Plot of the Reaction Rate

Appendix: Reference

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